

The Impact of Work Life Balance on Organizational Commitment: A Study Based on Financial Institutions

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Abstract

In today's fast-paced and interconnected world, managing the psychological well-being of employees holds a significant place. A stress-free workforce can produce amazing output. Maintaining a stable work behavior can help employees to keep the best balance between their personal and professional life to provide immense service to the organization. This study mainly investigates, the effects of work-life balance and organizational commitment in financial institutions. Further, it examines the level of variables, relationships and impacts between 'Work life balance and Organizational Commitment'. This study is descriptive and data collection was done using a structured questionnaire with closed-ended statements, measured with ordinal measures called Likert's Five-Point Rating Scale. The study population consists of employees of financial institutions in Batticaloa District. Applying the simple random sampling technique, 200 questionnaires were issued and from that, 141 duly filled questionnaires were received back. Study results revealed, a moderate level of work-life balance and high level of organizational commitment among the financial institution employees. A strong positive relationship found between work-life balance and organizational commitment (0.557). And regression result revealed a moderate positive impact (31.1%) of work life balance on organizational commitment. Further, the current study results confirm that by improving work-life balance, organizational commitment can be enhanced among employees.

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1. Introduction

People care more about their psychological state and well-being, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic (Hariri, et al (2024)). In shaping the psychological state of an employee, the support of their workplace plays a significant role. Thus, organizations consider mechanisms that could protect their employees from the busy, modern and highly demanding environment. Humans are social animals with growing needs. According to Abraham Maslow's need hierarchy, there are five levels, and with satisfying each level, humans expect further. Employees must find ways to satisfy their growing needs and manage the stressful and competitive working environment to lead a good life.

Another important concern to lead a comfortable life is psychological health. However, the competitive global stance has burdened employees with several problems on both professional and personal sides. An employee who pays more attention to work matters or vice versa loses the balance between work life and family life. In both ways, this can negatively impact the employee's life. The imbalance between work and family life seems to be a root cause for many family, mental and health issues. Increase of stress levels and unmanageable problems can cost employees happiness and satisfaction in life. This ultimately impacts not only the individual but also the whole organization. Thus, employees should develop abilities to maintain the balance between their work life and family life.

On the other hand, for any organization, the lifeline is its employees. an organization need committed and loyal workforce for it to survive and fight back in competitive settings. the psychological state of the employee matters in the delivery of high performance and productivity. Organizations do care about their employees; thus, organizations introduce mechanisms such as flex time, hybrid work arrangements, employee wellness programmes, a proper office setting and etc.

As organizations longed for committed workforce, to achieve that, they focus on job attitudes of employees. One of such attitudes is Work life balance, which plays an important role in shaping employee behavior in modern world. The concept of work life balance recommends to maintain a balance between work life and personnel life. By maintaining the balance, employees can satisfy their personal need at the same time, organizations also can achieve their success. Work-life balance can also be used as motivational tool among employees. Work-life balance helps an organization to reduce absenteeism and increase productivity, performance, loyalty, motivation and commitment among employees. An employee who maintains this balance leads a happier, positive and stress-free life along with good health and wellbeing.

In recent years, many organizations have been concerned about challenges of maintaining work and family life balance. Many employees came across severe pressure in managing their work and family life due to competitions, globalization, downsizing, changes that arise with the work patterns and technological changes. Highly competitive industries like financial sectors also have its impact. Due to the unbalance in employee's work and family life, banks were ultimately end up with produced dissatisfied work force (Tanvi & Fathma 2012, Burchell et al. 2002 as cited in Weerasooriyaarachchi, 2016).

Presently, there are many financial institutions operating in both public and private sectors of Sri Lanka. Since the services provided are similar, which creates the high competition and thus, have high expectations on employees. This has high chances that employees can easily expose to the imbalance and burnout and ultimately impact the performance of entire organization. Applying the concept of work-life balance will be supportive to both employees and organization to manage the commitment level effectively.

Due to the importance of work life balance and organizational commitment, many studies were carried out in these variables. Most of the studies have been carried out in different countries based on different sectors connected with many variables such as organizational commitment, job satisfaction, job performance and so on. However, the studies on the relationship and impact of work-life balance on organizational commitment investigated in the Sri Lankan

context seem to be fewer in number. And also, different study results have been reported even though majority of the study finding suggest the positive connection (Khan, Roy and Hossain, 2018; Inegbedion, 2024; Hotama & Setiorini, 2025). Thus, this study tries to examine the impact of work-life balance on organizational commitment among employees of financial institutions in Batticaloa district and investigate the relationship among these variables. So, the prime objective of this research is to “*investigate the impact of Work Life Balance on Organizational Commitment*”. It specifically aimed to generate information to identify relationship and impact between variables and development of proper actions to manage organizational commitment.

To accomplish the main objective, the specific sub objectives are identified as follows:

- To individually identify the level of work life balance and organizational commitment in financial institutions.
- To identify the relationship between work life balance and organizational commitment.
- To find out the impact of work life balance on organizational commitment.
- To suggest the organization to improve the organizational commitment through managing work life balance.

2. Review of Literature

Highly committed workforce creates great value to organizations. As organizational success depends on their employees, organizations look forward to encourage job behaviors such as loyalty, commitment, organizational citizenship behavior among employees. One of the prominent variables investigated broadly due to its essential role is organizational commitment. In simple words, organizational commitment is a bond between employee and their workplace. O'Reilly (1989) defines it as, “an individual's psychological bond to the organization, including a sense of job involvement, loyalty and belief in the values of the organization”. Organizational commitment is broader concept, including loyalty and willingness to work towards achieving company's goals.

The organizational commitment benefits firms by reducing absenteeism and turnover among staff, enhancing high performance and productivity, and encouraging them to work long for the organization (Nafei, 2014, as cited in Morhead & Griffin, 1998 and Moghimi, 2001). This also helps employees to maintain a high satisfaction level, reduce stress levels, enhanced wellbeing, and secure and enhance their careers. As this concept is so essential, this was explored by many previous scholars in connecting with many different concepts such as Organizational citizenship behavior (Morrison, 1994), Job satisfaction (Smith, Near and Organ, 1983; Jackinda & Judith, 2016) Stress (Lambert et al., 2005), work life balance (Hotama & Setiorini, 2025), Job involvement, Job performance, loyalty (Khan, et.al, 2014) etc.

However, due to the work burden and high competition, significant demands arise from professional side every day. Swamped with deadlines and targets, the employees have high chances to be exposed to high stress. Excess stress, known as distress, is harmful to the individual (Selye, 1974), limits their performance level and their mental and physical health. This type of conflict paved the way for the consideration of concepts such as work-life balance. Work-life balance is a primary driver of well-being.

Work-life balance is a concept about maintaining a balance between personal and professional demands. In 2003, Lockwood defined work life balance as a process of managing work and personal responsibilities. Many organizations sense, that work life balance helps to retain employees in organization, reduce work-family conflict, absenteeism and employee stress, increase satisfaction level and better life balance (Susi, 2010, Jackinda & Judith, 2016; Weerasooriyaarachchi, 2016; Tausig and Fenwick, 2021). By supporting work life balance, organizations approach employees to create a bond with the organization. On the flip side, this also assists employees to taking care of their personal responsibilities, increases satisfaction and maintain psychical and psychological health.

Work-life balance is affected by many factors such as job satisfaction, telework, job demands, stress level, etc., as well have its influence on many variables. Since work-life balance support to lower absenteeism and boost the motivation, engagement, commitment, well-being and

satisfaction of employees (Tausig and Fenwick, 2021), this can be fruitful to the industries which operating in high competitive market and faces high stress like banks, insurance, finance companies. This way they can ensure the staff retainment in their organizations.

Work-life balance has been investigated from different point of views; some studies explored the connection between demographics and work-life balance (Shakya, 2023; Ali et al., 2025), factors influencing employees' work-life balance (Vyas & Shrivastava, 2017; Basnet, et al., 2023;) as well some studies connected work-life balance with other variables such as well-being (Hoffmann-Burdzińska and Rutkowska, 2015), satisfaction (Pathak & Bhayani. 2025), employee commitment (Oyewobi et. al.,2019) , motivation (Oktosatrio, 2018) performance (Nwafor et. al., 2025) etc.

Many scholars have investigated the work-life balance and organizational commitment together. A major revelation from their studies was that work-life balance plays a significant role in improving organizational commitment. (Shakthivel & Jeyakrishnan, 2012; Kopp, 2013; Arif & Farooqi, 2014; Sethi, 2014; Shabir & Gani, 2019; Oyewobi et. al., 2019; Emrea & De Spiegeleareb, 2021; Mengistu & Worku, 2020; Inegbedion, 2024). The study has also considered different sectors such as healthcare workers (Azeem & Akhtar, 2014), bank employees (Mengistu & Worku, 2020), etc. Across different industries, the majority of the results were similar.

However, the results were not always the same; there were deviating results. Study results of Hotama & Setiorini, conducted in 2025 shows that Work-life balance (WLB) does not significantly affect Organizational Commitment (OC). A study conducted in Sri Lanka in 2024 indicates a negative and insignificant relationship between Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment (Shyamadhanthi & Kaluarachhige, 2023). Study of Khan, Roy and Hossain (2018) found week relationship between these variables. Due to the different results, the need for more exploration in this study area still exists.

3. Methodology

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This research is a quantitative study. This study uses statistical data as a medium to obtain needed information. Therefore, the findings are solely depending on the collected statistical data. This study determines the relations and impact between the independent and dependent variables. This research includes work-life balance and organizational commitment as main variables of study. On which, work life balance serves as the independent variable and organizational commitment is the dependent variable. This study employs cross-sectional analysis to analyze the collected data. The geographical boundary for the research study is Batticaloa District; thus, population for this study is employees who work in the financial institutions in Batticaloa District. This study employs a simple random sampling technique and intends to collect 200 samples. This study uses a questionnaire to collect the data. The research uses questionnaire with closed-ended questions with ordinal measures called Likert's Five-Points Rating Scale to require respondents to order their answers. 200 questionnaires were shared with the employees of the financial institution in Batticaloa district and 141 duly filled questionnaires were received back. The collected data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS – Version 19.0) package. The level of variable was analyzed by analysis of mean and standard deviation. Correlation and regression analysis were performed to analyze the relationship and impact between variables. Secondary data for this study collected from books, publications, journal articles, e-sources, previously conducted research and reports, and other relevant documents to provide theoretical support for the study.

4. Result & Discussion

Reliability analysis

The Reliability of an instrument was measured using cronbach's alpha test. In general, reliabilities less than 0.60 are considered to be poor, those in the 0.70 range is acceptable, those over 0.80 good and those over 0.90 excellent.

Table 1: Reliability analysis

Variables	Cronbach's alpha
Work Life Balance	0.890
Organizational Commitment	0.951

(Source: Survey data)

The overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.935 with respect to 33 statements. Therefore, all items considered in this study are to be reliable, which suggest that the internal reliability of the instrument was satisfactory.

Personal information

Descriptive statistical analysis was run on respondents' demographic variables.

Table 2: Summary of demographic information

Demographic Profile		Frequencies	Percentages (%)
Age groups	21 – 30 Years	71	50.4%
	31 – 40 Years	62	44.0%
	41 – 50 Years	05	3.5%
	Over 50 Years	03	2.1%
Gender	Male	94	66.7%
	Female	47	33.3%
Civil Status	Single	56	39.7%
	Married	85	60.3%

Educational Qualification	Advanced Level	48	34.0%
	Graduate	59	41.8%
	Masters/ Professional	34	24.1%
Working experience	Less than 03 Years	48	34.0%
	03 to 07 Years	45	31.9%
	07 to 10 Years	26	18.4%
	More than 10 Years	22	15.6%
Monthly Income	Below 25,000	18	12.8%
	25,000 to 50,000	31	22.0%
	50,000 to 75,000	30	21.3%
	75,000 to 100,000	30	21.3%
	Above 100,000	32	22.7%
Job Category	Staff Level	55	39.0%
	Executive Level	69	48.9%
	Manager Level	17	12.1%

(Source: Survey Data)

From among four categories of age group majority of the respondents are from 21 to 30 years (50.4%). Out of 141 respondent's majority of the respondents are males (66.7%) and 60.3% are married. Majority of respondents are graduates (41.8%). 65% of sample comprises with employees who have more than 3 years of experience. Sample includes relatively similar percentage of employees in each income category comprising 12.8%, 22%, 21.3%, 21.3% and 22.7% respectively. From the respondents 39% are from staff level, 48.9% are from executive level and 12.1% are manager level.

Research Information

Research information considered two main variables such as Work Life Balance and Organizational commitment.

Level of variables

Table 3: Level of variables

Dimensions/ Variable	Mean	S.D
Work life balance	3.153546	.5643451
Organizational Commitment	4.076241	.7648976

According to the results, there is a moderate level of Work Life Balance in Batticaloa District with mean value of 3.15. In addition to this most of the employees have common opinion regarding the Work Life Balance (Standard Deviation = 0.564). According to the results, there is a high level of Organizational Commitment in Batticaloa District with mean value of 4.08. In addition to this most of the employees have common opinion regarding the Organizational Commitment (Standard Deviation = 0.765).

Relationship between Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

The table shows the Pearson's correlation between the Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment of financial institutions in Batticaloa District.

Table 4: Relationship between Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

		Work life balance	Organizational Commitment
Work life balance	Pearson Correlation	1	.557**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	141	141

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

(Source: Survey Data)

Based on the above table the coefficient of correlation (R) of Work Life Balance is greater than 0.5 and it is found as strong positive (0.557) correlation at the significance level 0.000 (2-tailed). It indicates that the correlation was significant and relationships are linearly correlated. So, there is correlation between two variables. Since correlation is positive it can be said that there is a positive relationship between two variables, Work Life Balance of financial institution employees would help to increase level of Organizational Commitment.

Impact of Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

Impact of Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment is calculated by using simple regression analysis.

Table 5: Model Summary of Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.557 ^a	.311	.306	.6373380

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work life balance

Table 5: Model Summary of Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.557 ^a	.311	.306	.6373380

(Source: Survey Data)

The model summary of simple linear regression shows, R (0.557) is correlation coefficient between Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment. It says that there is a strong positive correlation between Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment. R square is 0.311. Therefore, it can conclude that 31.1% of variability in Organizational Commitment is accounted by the Work Life Balance. In other words, 68.9% of variance of Organizational Commitment was affected by other variables.

Table 6: Coefficients of Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.694	.306		5.540	.000
	Work life balance	.755	.095	.557	7.915	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment

(Source: Survey Data)

The β coefficients for Work Life Balance is 0.755. The β -coefficient shows that every unit of increase in Work Life Balance increases the Organizational Commitment by 0.755. Therefore, study concluded as Work Life Balance has positive effect on Organizational Commitment at financial institutions in Batticaloa

Therefore, the regression equation model is as follows:

$$\text{Organizational Commitment} = 1.694 + 0.755 (\text{Work Life Balance})$$

Current study's results show that strong positive relationship between Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment. The results are consistent with results of Shakthivel & Jeyakrishnan (2012), Kopp (2013), Arif & Farooqi (2014), Sethi (2014), Shabir and Gani (2019), Oyewobi et. al. (2019), Emrea & De Spiegeleareb (2021), Mengistu & Worku (2020), Inegbedion (2024) which displayed similar results, positive relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment. However, the results not aligned with the results of Shyamadhanthi & Kaluarachchige, (2023) and Hotama & Setiorini, (2025), that displayed non significance relationship. Current study is displaying a strong positive relationship among variables unlike the study of Khan, Roy and Hossain (2018), which found weak relationship.

Although the study results say the strong positive relationship, the correlation is near the border. And the regression results display a moderate impact of variables. At the same time, the level of work life balance is also in moderate level among the staff. So, organizations should work hard in increasing the work-life balance among employees. As work-life balance has influence of many behavioral variables and factors. Targeting them will help to enhance the level of work-life balance, while maintaining a strong commitment from employees.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The success and long-term achievement of organizations depend on their employees. In retaining cheerful employees, the good working environment plays a significant role. The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of Work Life Balance on Organizational Commitment. Research findings highlighted that there is a moderate level of Work Life Balance and high level of Organizational Commitment in Batticaloa District. The relationship among Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment is strong, positive and significant ($R = 0.557$). As well 31.1% of variability in Organizational Commitment is explained by Work Life Balance.

Since the study results are like this, work-life balance can be used as a mechanism to enhance the commitment level of employees under the current settings. Managers can use some strategies such as encouraging teamwork, secure jobs, conflict management skill development, stress handling training, providing superior support, and close relationships between subordinates to increase the work-life balance among their employees.

Providing a suitable work environment is very important to their performance and allows them to give their full potential to the workplace. If the environment is not suitable for them to perform, employees can be negatively impacted and stressed. A comfortable work environment can be provided through offering essential organizational support, setting realistic targets, enough time to perform the task, well managed work hours, provide proper guidance, clear instructions and information. Application of hybrid work models, flex time models, anxiety free environment can help to boost the work-life balance. Further, factors such as job involvement, work role conflict, job stress, work role ambiguity, and engagement can also be considered in managing the desired level of work-life balance. This can influence the factors which triggers work life balance and support employees to manage the stress that caused in workplaces. By managing the Work Life Balance, significant increase in organizational commitment among employees can be achieved since both variables are expressing strong positive relationship and a moderate level of impact.

On the other hand, according to the findings, 31.1% of variability in organizational commitment is accounted by the work-life balance and 68.9% of variance of organizational commitment was affected by other variables. Thus, Managers need to focus on the factors other than work-life balance which can influence on organizational commitment such as satisfaction, motivation, training, leadership, role at organization, etc., in enhancing the organizational commitment. Also, future studies can consider and explore the other variables in defining organizational commitment. The studies can further extend to other regions and other relevant service sectors with increased sample size.

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REFERENCES

- Ali, S., Ishrat, A., Barthwal, T., Ali, N., Singh, R. R., & Singh, A. (2025). Unveiling the nexus: Exploring how demographic factors shape work-life balance for women professionals. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 15(2), 390–394. <https://doi.org/10.32479/irmm.17486>
- Arif, B., & Farooqi, Y. A. (2014). Impact of work life balance on job satisfaction and organizational commitment among university teachers: A case study of University of Gujrat, Pakistan. *International journal of multidisciplinary sciences and engineering*, 5(9), 24-29.
- Azeem, S. M., & Akhtar, N. (2014). The influence of work life balance and job satisfaction on organizational commitment of healthcare employees. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(2), 18.
- Basnet, S., Devkota, N., Dhakal, K., Puri, V., & Paudel, U. R. (2023). Factors influencing employees' work-life balance in commercial banks of Nepal: Evidence from structural equation modeling. *Quest Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 132-147. <https://doi.org/10.3126/qjmss.v5i1.56299>
- Burchell, B. J., Ladipo, D., & Wilkinson, F. (2002). Job insecurity and work intensification. London: Routledge. In Weerasooriyaarachchi, W.A.P.D. (2016). Impact Of Work Life Balance On Job Satisfaction Of Non Managerial Employees In Selected Private Banks In Colombo District. 3rd International HRM Conference,3(1): 230-235
- Emre, O., & De Spiegelaere, S. (2021). The role of work–life balance and autonomy in the relationship between commuting, employee commitment and well-being.

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT, 32(11),
2443–2467. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2019.1583270>

Hariri, N. I. M., Othman, W. N. W., Anuar, S. B. A., Lin, T. Y., & Zainudin, Z. N. (2024). Effect of work-life balance on employees' well-being. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 12(12), 705–718.

Ho, W. H., Chang, C. S., Shih, Y. L., & Liang, R. D. (2009). Effects of job rotation and role stress among nurses on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *BMC health services research*, 9(1), 8.

Hoffmann-Burdzińska, K., & Rutkowska, M. (2015). Work life balance as a factor influencing well-being. *Journal of Positive Management*, 6(4), 87–101.

Hotama, V. A., & Setiorini, A. (2025). The effect of work-life balance, self-esteem, and work motivation on organizational commitment of Gen Z employees. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(4), 738–750. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.90400055>

Inegbedion HE (2024) Work-life balance and employee commitment: mediating effect of job satisfaction. *Front. Psychol.* 15:1349555. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1349555

Jackinda & Judith, (2016). Influence of Work Life Balance On Job Satisfaction Of Employees In Milimani Law Courts, Nairobi, Kenya. University Of Nairobi, <Http://Hdl.Handle.Net/11295/99965>

Khan, F., Rasli, A. M., Yusoff, R. M., Ahmed, T., Rehman, A. U., & Khan, M. M. (2014). Job rotation, job performance, organizational commitment: An empirical study on bank employees. *Journal of Management Info*, 1(3), 11–17.

Khan, M. R., Roy, M. K., & Hossain, S. M. K. (2018). Bankers' work-life balance and organizational commitment: Exploring the dominant factors to move on job-family life balance. *Journal of Business and Management Executive Research*, 2(10).

- Kopp, L. R. (2013). The effects of perceived supervisor work-life support on employee work-life balance, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior (Doctoral dissertation, University of Wisconsin--Stout).
- Lambert, E. G., Hogan, N. L., Paoline, E. A., III, & Clarke, A. (2005). The impact of role stressors on job stress, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment among private prison staff. *Security Journal*, 18(4), 33–50.
- Lockwood, N. (2003). Work Life Balance; Challenges And Solutions. *Journal Of Management*, 17(3), 1-12
- Mathew, R. V., & Panchanatham, N. (2010). An empirical analysis of the impact of various dimensions of work-life balance on organizational commitment among service sector employees in India. *International Journal of Management Studies (IJMS)*, 17(1), 129-147.
- Mengistu, A. B., & Worku, M. M. (2020). Effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. *Journal of Strategic Human Resource Management*, 9(2/3).
- Moghimi, S., (2001). *Management And Organization, Research Approaches*, Tehran, Termeh Publication.
- Morhead, J., And Griffin, R., (1998). *Organizational Behavior, Translation*, Tehran, Morvarid Publication. In Nafei, W. A. (2014, January). Do Job Rotation And Role Stress Affect Job Attitudes? A Study From Egyptian Context. *American International Journal Of Social Science*, 3(1). Retrieved From Http://Www.Aijssnet.Com/Journals/Vol_3_No_1_January_2014/9.Pdf
- Morrison, E. W. 1994. Role definitions and organizational citizenship behavior: The importance of the employee's perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 37: 1543-1567.

- Nafei, W. A. (2014, January). Do Job Rotation And Role Stress Affect Job Attitudes? A Study From Egyptian Context. *American International Journal Of Social Science*, 3(1). Retrieved From [Http://Www.Aijssnet.Com/Journals/Vol_3_NO_1_January_2014/9.Pdf](http://Www.Aijssnet.Com/Journals/Vol_3_NO_1_January_2014/9.Pdf)
- Nwafor, A. E., Maranzu, C., & Oti, E. I. (2025). Work life balance initiative and job satisfaction. *International Journal of Public Administration and Development Studies*, 2(1), 166–185.
- Okotosatrio, S. (2018). Investigating the relationship between work-life-balance and motivation of the employees: Evidences from the local government of Jakarta. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(2), 205–221.
- O'Reilly, C. A., III. 1989. Corporations, Culture, And Commitment: Motivation And Social Control In Organizations. *California Management Review*, 31(4): 9-25.
- Oyewobi, L. O., Oke, A. E., Adeneye, T. D., & Jimoh, R. A. (2019). Influence of organizational commitment on work–life balance and organizational performance of female construction professionals. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 26(10), 2243–2263. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-07-2018-0277>
- Pathak, S., & Bhayani, S. (2025). A study on work-life balance and its impact on job satisfaction among employees of Saurashtra, India. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 25(7), 578–585. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2025/v25i71909>
- Sakthivel, D., & Jayakrishnan, J. (2012). Work life balance and Organizational commitment for Nurses. *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 2(5), 1-6.
- Sethi, U. J. (2014). Influence of work life balance on organisational commitment: a comparative study of women employees working in public and private sector Banks. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(34), 215-219.
- Selye, H. (1974). *Stress without distress*. J.B. Lippincott Company.

- Shabir, S., & Gani, A. (2020). Impact of work–life balance on organizational commitment of women health-care workers: Structural modeling approach. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 28(4), 917-939.
- Shakya, S. (2023). A study of demographic variables on work life balance among employees working in commercial banks in Nepal. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 3(1), 1–11.
- Shyamadhanthi, D., & Kaluarachchige, I. P. (2023). Impact of work life balance on job satisfaction with mediating relationships of employee engagement and organizational commitment. *Journal of Human Resource Management Perspectives*, 8(2), 45-56.
- Smith, C. A., Organ, D. W., & Near, J. P. (1983). Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Its Nature and Antecedents. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 68(4), 653-663.
http://130.18.86.27/faculty/warkentin/SecurityPapers/Merrill/SmithOrganNear1983_JAP_OCB.pdf
- Susi.S, J. (2010). Work-Life Balance: The Key Driver Of Employee Engagement. *Asian Journal Of Management Research*, 1-10.
- Tanvi, N.M., and Fatima, Z.K., (2012), Work-life balance: Is it still a new concept in private commercial banking sector of Bangladesh, *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*. 1(2), 57-66.
- Tausig, M., & Fenwick, R. (2001). Unbinding time: Alternate work schedules and work-life balance. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 22(2), 101–119.
- Vyas, A., & Shrivastava, D. (2017). Factors affecting work life balance - A review. *Productivity: A Quarterly Journal of the National Productivity Council*, 57(4), 398–404.
- Weerasooriyaarachchi, W.A.P.D. (2016). Impact Of Work Life Balance On Job Satisfaction Of Non Managerial Employees In Selected Private Banks In Colombo District. 3rd International HRM Conference, 3(1): 230-235